

X-Ray Analysis of Two Highly Energetic Flares from AB Dor Observed by XMM-Newton

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Abstract

We present a detailed analysis of the two strong X-ray superflares from AB Dor observed by XMM-Newton satellite as observed on 02 January 2011 and 07 October 2016. These flares, F1, and F2 were found to last for around 1 hr and 3 hr, respectively with a total energy release of 10^{34-36} erg in which the peak flare flux increased up to 34 times from the pre-/post-flaring states for the strongest observed flare (F2). The quiescent state of AB Dor was found to be explained by a three-temperature plasma with average temperatures of 0.29, 0.99, and 2.85 keV, respectively. The temperatures, emission measures, abundance, and hydrogen column density are found to be varying during the flares. The peak X-ray luminosity and the peak temperature of these flares F1 and F2 are found to be 3.29×10^{30} erg/s and ~ 43 MK, 82.6×10^{30} erg/s and 92 MK, respectively. By employing the hydrodynamic loop model, the semi-loop lengths of flares F1 and F2 are found to be 1.3 and 5×10^{10} cm, respectively.

1 Introduction

Stellar flares are sudden and short outbursts of intense energy in the stellar atmosphere, caused by the release of magnetic energy stored in the star's corona. These events result in increased excess emission in X-rays to radio wavelengths and produce a significant impact on the stellar environment. In the past, stellar X-ray flares have been extensively studied by several authors (e.g. Pallavicini *et al.*, 1990; Getman *et al.*, 2008; Pandey & Singh, 2008, 2012). They come in a variety of shapes, sizes, and duration ranging from a few minutes to a few hours, and with the released energy in the range of 10^{30-38} erg s^{-1} . The energy release during flares can be explained by magnetic reconnection processes (Parker, 1988; Benz & Güdel, 2010). In the standard model of flares, magnetic reconnection causes a rapid and transient release of magnetic energy in the corona, leading to particle acceleration and emission of electromagnetic radiation, ranging from radio waves to γ -rays. These charged particles gyrate downward along magnetic field lines, producing synchrotron radio emission, and when they collide with denser chromospheric materials, they produce hard X-rays. The simultaneous heating of plasma to tens of millions of Kelvin evaporates cool material from chromospheric footpoints, increasing the density of newly formed coronal loops and emitting UV and soft X-rays.

Stellar coronae are nearly 1000 times brighter than the Sun, making the flares on stars more energetic and impulsive compared to the Sun. Flares with energy releases $\geq 10^{33}$ erg s^{-1} are referred to as superflares (Schaefer *et al.*, 2000; Shibayama *et al.*, 2013; Tsuboi *et al.*, 2016). This paper presents a detailed analysis of strong X-ray flares observed in the active star AB Dor A. AB Dor A is part of the AB Doradus quintuplet stellar system located 15.0 ± 0.1 pc away (Guirado *et al.*, 1997). The other companions, AB Dor Ca/Cb

(Climent *et al.*, 2019) and AB Dor Ba/Bb (Vilhu & Linsky, 1987) are not considered in this study due to their negligible contribution in the observed X-ray. AB Dor A is a young and active K0V spectral type star with a rotational period of 0.5148 days (Pakull, 1981). Its high spin rate causes frequent flaring activity and a strong magnetic field. AB Dor A has a radius of $\sim 0.96 R_{\odot}$, a mass of $0.86 M_{\odot}$, and a surface temperature of 5081 K (see Guirado *et al.*, 2011, and references therein). Most X-ray observatories have detected frequent flares in AB Dor A's corona (e.g. Pakull, 1981; Vilhu *et al.*, 1993; Kuerster *et al.*, 1997, etc.). Vilhu *et al.* (1993) were the first to report on statistical studies of X-ray flares, finding a mean flare energy of $\sim 10^{34}$ erg, putting AB Dor A as a frequently super-flaring star. Lalitha (2016) later expanded on this work using XMM-Newton data, finding a similar scaling law between flare peak emission and temperature as what is seen in the Sun. In this study, we conducted a detailed analysis of X-ray flares on AB Dor A using XMM-Newton Observatory. The paper is organized as follows. The Observations and the principle procedures of data reduction are given in Section 2. In Section 3, we have explained the analysis procedure in detail and showed the scientific results obtained from X-ray timing and spectral analysis. Finally, in Sections 4 and 5, we have discussed the results and presented our conclusion.

2 Observations and Data Reduction

The present study analyzes two X-ray observations of AB Dor A made using the XMM-Newton satellite. The first observation was taken on February 1st, 2011 (0412580701, S1) for a duration of 56 ks, while the second was taken on July 10th, 2016 (0791980101, S2) for a duration of 98 ks.

The XMM-Newton satellite is equipped with three co-aligned X-ray telescopes, each featuring five X-ray detec-

Figure 1: The background subtracted X-ray light curves of AB Dor for different epochs of observations. Light curves from PN, MOS, and RGS detectors are shown in blue, black, and red colours, respectively. The hardness ratio from the PN detector is plotted in green, where H is the count rate in the hard X-ray band (2-10 keV) and S is the count rate in the soft X-ray band (0.3-2 keV).

tors: one PN detector (as outlined in Strüder *et al.* (2001)) and two MOS detectors (as outlined in Turner *et al.* (2001)) from the EPIC cameras, and two RGS detectors (as outlined in den Herder *et al.* (2001)). The EPIC cameras provide moderate spectral resolution, with a resolving power of ~ 20 -50 in the energy range of 0.1 – 15 keV. Meanwhile, the RGS instruments offer a better spectral resolution, with a resolving power of 150 – 800 in the energy range of 0.33 - 2.5 keV (or 5 - 35 Å).

The EPIC and RGS data reduction was performed using the XMM-Newton’s Science Analysis System (SAS) software version 18.0.0, along with updated calibration files. The raw EPIC data was processed to generate event files using `EPPROC` and `EMPROC` for PN and MOS data, respectively. No intense proton background flaring events were observed. Pile-up effects were analyzed using `EPATPLOT`, and annulus regions with inner and outer radii of 7.5" and 55", and 20" and 68", respectively, were selected to mitigate the pile-up effect for sets S1 and S2. EPIC observations’ X-ray light curves were corrected for background and other effects using `EPICLCCORR`. `ESPECGET` was utilized to generate source and background spectra, along with the corresponding RMF and ARF files. All X-ray spectra were binned to have a minimum of 20 counts per bin using `GRPPHA`. The raw RGS data was reduced using `RGSPROC` to produce event files and other spectral products. The task `RGSLCCORR` was used to create combined RGS1 and RGS2 light curves.

3 Analysis and Results

3.1 X-ray light curves

The top three panels of Figure 1 display the X-ray light curves of AB Dor obtained from the EPIC and RGS instruments after subtracting the background, in the energy ranges of 0.3 – 10 keV and 0.33 – 2.07 keV, respectively. The bot-

tom panels show the time evolution of the hardness ratio (HR), which is defined as $(H-S)/(H+S)$, where H represents the count rate in the hard energy range of 2.0 – 10.0 keV, and S is the count rate in the soft energy range of 0.3 – 2.0 keV. Regions of constant HR beyond the flaring regions were designated as pre- or post-flare epochs and were marked as P1 for set S1, while P2 and P3 for set S2 in Figure 1. Flares were identified by searching for HR excursions greater than three times the standard deviation in pre- and post-flare light curves. This approach revealed two major flares, labelled as F1 and F2 in Figure 1, with flare-to-quietest count rate ratio (F/Q) of ~ 2 and ~ 34 , respectively. The light curves for both flares were modelled using an exponential rise and decay model using RGS data, as the PN detectors do not cover the entire observation period. The rise and decay times for flare F1 were found to be 0.36 ± 0.05 ks and 1.09 ± 0.09 ks, while those for flare F2 were 0.52 ± 0.02 ks and 2.19 ± 0.05 ks, respectively.

3.2 X-ray Spectral analysis

In this section, we delve into the X-ray spectral analysis of AB Dor using XMM-Newton observations. To monitor changes in X-ray spectral parameters, we conducted time-resolved spectroscopy (TRS) with data from the PN detector, which provides better statistics for low-exposure spectra. We chose P1 and P2 as proxies for the quiescent state and modelled the extracted X-ray spectra to determine plasma temperature, emission measure, and abundance. The quiescent spectra were fitted with one temperature (1-T), two temperatures (2-T), and three temperatures (3-T) plasma models `APEC` (Smith *et al.*, 2001). All temperatures, emission measures, interstellar hydrogen column density (N_H), and global abundances (Z) were treated as free parameters during fitting. The X-ray absorption model `TBABS` (Wilms *et al.*, 2000) was used to account for N_H , while the solar photospheric abundances

Table 1: Best fit spectral parameters from the pre/post-flare spectra using 3-T APEC model for all data sets.

Flare	S	kT_1	kT_2	kT_3	EM_1	EM_2	EM_3	$Z(Z_\odot)$	N_H	L_X	χ^2_ν (dof)
S1	P1	$0.29^{+0.01}_{-0.01}$	$0.99^{+0.01}_{-0.01}$	$3.4^{+1.3}_{-0.8}$	$7.4^{+1.2}_{-1.3}$	$9.2^{+1.3}_{-1.7}$	$1.8^{+0.8}_{-0.5}$	$0.15^{+0.03}_{-0.02}$	$1.9^{+0.8}_{-0.8}$	$1.426^{+0.009}_{-0.009}$	1.07 (338)
F1	R	-	-	$3.7^{+0.4}_{-0.3}$	-	-	$6.4^{+0.4}_{-0.4}$	$0.22^{+0.01}_{-0.01}$	$0.9^{+0.5}_{-0.4}$	$2.03^{+0.03}_{-0.03}$	0.89 (208)
	P	-	-	$3.3^{+0.2}_{-0.2}$	-	-	$16.3^{+0.7}_{-0.7}$	$0.22^{+0.01}_{-0.01}$	<0.8	$3.29^{+0.04}_{-0.04}$	1.04 (230)
	D1	-	-	$2.5^{+0.2}_{-0.2}$	-	-	$11.2^{+0.6}_{-0.5}$	$0.25^{+0.01}_{-0.01}$	$1.1^{+0.4}_{-0.4}$	$2.53^{+0.03}_{-0.03}$	1.16 (252)
	D2	-	-	$2.2^{+0.1}_{-0.1}$	-	-	$7.2^{+0.5}_{-0.4}$	$0.20^{+0.01}_{-0.01}$	$0.4^{+0.4}_{-0.3}$	$1.85^{+0.02}_{-0.02}$	1.09 (228)
	D3	-	-	$1.9^{+0.2}_{-0.2}$	-	-	$4.3^{+0.4}_{-0.4}$	$0.19^{+0.01}_{-0.01}$	$0.4^{+0.3}_{-0.3}$	$1.50^{+0.02}_{-0.02}$	0.94 (216)
S2	P2	$0.281^{+0.006}_{-0.006}$	$0.99^{+0.01}_{-0.02}$	$2.3^{+0.7}_{-0.4}$	$7.8^{+1.0}_{-1.0}$	$9.6^{+1.2}_{-1.4}$	$1.8^{+0.8}_{-0.6}$	$0.17^{+0.02}_{-0.02}$	$1.4^{+0.6}_{-0.6}$	$1.502^{+0.007}_{-0.007}$	1.28 (411)
F2	R1	-	-	$6.1^{+0.4}_{-0.3}$	-	-	$29.9^{+0.6}_{-0.6}$	$0.23^{+0.01}_{-0.01}$	$0.5^{+0.3}_{-0.3}$	$6.48^{+0.05}_{-0.05}$	1.03 (411)
	R2	-	-	$7.4^{+0.3}_{-0.3}$	-	-	201^{+3}_{-3}	$0.43^{+0.03}_{-0.03}$	<0.5	$39.0^{+0.3}_{-0.3}$	1.09 (561)
	R3	-	-	$7.9^{+0.3}_{-0.3}$	-	-	315^{+5}_{-5}	$0.49^{+0.05}_{-0.05}$	<0.2	$61.7^{+0.4}_{-0.4}$	1.14 (557)
	R4	-	-	$6.6^{+0.3}_{-0.3}$	-	-	405^{+8}_{-8}	$0.40^{+0.05}_{-0.05}$	$0.4^{+0.3}_{-0.3}$	$74.1^{+0.6}_{-0.6}$	1.20 (472)
	R5	-	-	$5.9^{+0.2}_{-0.2}$	-	-	459^{+7}_{-7}	$0.40^{+0.04}_{-0.04}$	<0.3	$81.3^{+0.6}_{-0.6}$	1.05 (532)
	R6	-	-	$5.5^{+0.2}_{-0.2}$	-	-	444^{+9}_{-9}	$0.54^{+0.06}_{-0.06}$	<0.1	$81.1^{+0.7}_{-0.7}$	1.11 (432)
	P	-	-	$4.7^{+0.1}_{-0.1}$	-	-	493^{+9}_{-9}	$0.42^{+0.05}_{-0.05}$	<0.6	$82.6^{+0.7}_{-0.7}$	1.14 (451)

Note: All the temperatures and emission measures are in units of keV and 10^{52} cm^{-3} , respectively, whereas the hydrogen column density N_H and X-ray luminosity (L_X) are in units of 10^{20} cm^{-2} and $10^{30} \text{ erg s}^{-1}$, respectively. The dof is the number of degrees of freedom and χ^2_ν is the reduced χ^2 .

(Z_\odot) were taken from Anders & Grevesse (1989). The 3-T model was found to be a significantly better fit compared to the 1-T and 2-T models. Adding another more thermal component did not improve the χ^2 value. Table 1 summarizes the best-fit model parameters and reduced χ^2 values for P1 and P2. The model parameters for P1 and P2 are found to be similar within 1σ level.

In order to understand how the spectral parameters vary during flares, we divided the full flaring epochs (F1 and F2) into smaller time segments that represent the rising, peak, and decay phases. These phases are labeled as Ri, P, and Di, respectively. The time segments were chosen so that they have a similar and adequate number of counts for spectral analysis. Further, the spectra extracted from these time bins were fitted with the 3-T APEC model, with all parameters kept free during the fit. The first two temperatures were found to be similar to the quiescent temperatures, but the third temperature varied during the flare. To get the best spectral fit, we fixed the first two temperatures and emission measures at the quiescent level and let the rest of the parameters vary. We also tried fitting the spectra with a 3+1 T APEC model, but this did not improve the fit, so we used the previous model for further analysis. The best-fit spectral parameters, with 68% confidence range and reduced χ^2 values, are given in Table 1 and the temporal evolution of these parameters is shown in Figure 2. Figure 2 shows that the third temperature, T3, is highest during the rising phase of the flare. T3 was found to be 3.7 and 7.9 keV for flares F1 and F2, respectively. The variation in emission measure (EM_3), abundance (Z), and X-ray luminosity (L_X) were found to be in agreement with the standard flare model.

The densities of flaring and quiescent states were determined using the He-like triplets of O VII in the RGS spectra, which correspond to transitions from the $n = 2$ shell to the $n = 1$ ground state shell and are classified as resonance (r), intercombination (i), and forbidden (f) lines. The ratio $R = f/i$ is sensitive to density (n_e), while the ratio $G = (f + i)/r$ is sensitive to temperature (Porquet *et al.*, 2001; Gabriel & Jordan, 1969). The line fluxes were measured using XSPEC software, modelled with three Gaussian emission lines convolved with the instrument's response matrices. The Bremsstrahlung models were used as the continuum emission at the temperatures inferred from the RGS spectra analysis. Using the CHI-

ANTI atomic database version 7.1 (Dere *et al.*, 1997; Landi *et al.*, 2013), we calculated the density of flaring and quiescent plasma. The densities for quiescent states P1 and P2+P3 were found to be $1.0^{+1.0}_{-0.6}$ and $2.5^{+1.0}_{-0.3} \times 10^{10} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, while for flares F1 and F2 the corresponding densities are found to be <4.8 and $10^{+4}_{-2} \times 10^{10} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, respectively.

3.3 Loop Parameters

Stellar flares cannot be directly observed in terms of spatial resolution, however, by comparing them to solar flares and loop models, we can estimate the shape and size of the flaring loops and the corona. Data on these flares don't always capture the entire event, sometimes only the rising phase or the decay phase is seen. In our case, the PN detector only captured the rising phase of flare F2. Hence, we made separate calculations for loop length during the rising phase (cited in Reale (2007)) and decay phase (cited in Reale *et al.* (1997)) using a Hydrodynamic loop model. These models assume a single dominating loop with constant cross section and constant cooling during the decay phase of the flare, however, Reale *et al.* (1997) took into account plasma cooling as well as heating during the flare decay by adding a correction factor ($F(\zeta)$), where ζ represents the slope of the density vs. temperature curve. The calculated loop lengths for the rising phase (L_r) and decay phase (L_d) for the flares F1 and F2 are given in Table 2. The $\log\sqrt{EM}$ vs. $\log(T)$ curve for flare F1 is shown in Figure 3 with a slope (ζ) of 0.9.

The total plasma density is a combination of electron density and hydrogen ion density (n_H), where n_H is found to be 0.8 times n_e . Using the maximum flare temperature ($T_{max} = 0.13 T_0^{1.16}$), peak plasma density (n_e), and peak emission measure (EM), the plasma pressure ($p = 1.8n_en_e kT_{max}$), flaring loop volume ($V = \frac{EM}{0.8n_e^2}$), and minimum magnetic field ($B_{min} = \sqrt{8\pi p}$) at the loop apex required to confine the plasma in the corona were derived. The calculated values of p , V , and B_{min} are given in Table 2.

The estimated loop lengths of AB Dor are much smaller than the pressure scale height of the plasma. Hence, the flaring loops are close to a steady state, and the RTV scaling law (Rosner *et al.*, 1978) can be used to estimate the plasma's physical parameters (as described in Aschwanden *et al.*, 2008). The heating rate per unit volume (HR_V) at the

Figure 2: Temporal evolution of the spectral parameters of AB Dor during flares and quiescent states, where top to bottom plots show the variation of X-ray luminosity in units of 10^{30} erg s^{-1} , emission measure (EM_3) in units of 10^{52} cm^{-3} , temperature (T_3) in units of 10^7 K, and relative abundance (Z/Z_{\odot}).

Figure 3: Flare evolution in the $\log\sqrt{EM}$ vs. $\log(T)$ curve during the decay phase of flare F1 along with the best fit linear curve.

flare peak can be calculated using the RTV relationship:

$$HR_V \sim 10^5 p^{7/6} L^{-5/6} \quad (1)$$

Assuming a constant heating rate during both the rising and decaying phases of the flare, the total heating rate (E_{HR}) and total energy ($E_{H,Total}$) corresponding to the heating rate can be estimated as:

$$E_{HR} \sim HR_V \times V; \quad E_{H,Total} = E_{HR} \times (\tau_r + \tau_d) \quad (2)$$

Here, τ_r and τ_d represent the rise and decay time of the flare, respectively. If we assume that the energy released

Flare (\rightarrow)	F1	F2
L_{XF} (10^{31} erg s^{-1})	1.119 ± 0.007	$>42.6^a$
$E_{X,Total}$ (10^{34} erg)	1.6 ± 0.1	$>115^a$
t_M (ks)	1.675	1.95
T_0 (MK)	43 ± 4	92 ± 4
T_M (MK)	38 ± 2	54 ± 1
L_r (10^{10} cm)	1.3 ± 0.3	5.0 ± 0.6
L_d (10^{10} cm)	1.2 ± 0.2	-
p (10^2 dyne cm^{-2})	<11	56 ± 17
V (10^{31} cm^3)	>9	62 ± 37
B_{min} (G)	<167	374 ± 57
B_{Total} (G)	<276	577 ± 98
E_{HR} (10^{31} erg s^{-1})	~ 12	175 ± 48
$E_{H,Total}$ (10^{34} erg)	~ 17	474 ± 131

^a Parameters derived using only the rise phase of the flare.

during the flare is of magnetic origin, we can calculate the total non-potential magnetic field (B_{Total}) within the star's active region that corresponds to the energy released during the flare. The B_{Total} can be determined by $E_{H,Total} = (B_{Total}^2 - B_{min}^2) \times V / 8\pi$. All the estimated loop parameters for AB Dor are listed in Table 2.

4 Discussion

In studies of flares, it is important to consider the quiescent emission in stars which always exist even during the flare. The quiescent corona of AB Dor can be characterized by three temperature plasma models, resulting in average

values of temperature and emission measure of 0.88 keV and $6.3 \times 10^{52} \text{ cm}^{-3}$. These findings are consistent with previous studies of AB Dor (e.g. Güdel *et al.*, 2001; Sanz-Forcada *et al.*, 2003; Lalitha, 2016). Three-temperature quiescent coronae have also been found in several RS CVn stars (Pandey & Pant, 2012) but with higher values of temperature and emission measure. The majority of active main sequence stars have quiescent coronae explained by two- or three-temperature plasma models (van den Oord *et al.*, 1988; Pandey & Singh, 2008; Pandey & Karmakar, 2015; Karmakar *et al.*, 2017, 2022; Pillitteri *et al.*, 2022; Singh & Pandey, 2022; Karmakar *et al.*, 2023).

We conducted a comprehensive study of two strong X-ray superflares on AB Dor and found the e-folding rise and decay times to be 0.36 and 1.09 ks for flare F1 and 0.52 and 2.19 ks for flare F2, displaying a rapid rise and slower decay pattern commonly seen in solar and stellar flares (van den Oord *et al.*, 1988; Pandey & Singh, 2008, 2012; Lalitha, 2016; Yan *et al.*, 2021). The F/Q ratio of flare F1 was ~ 2 , similar to previous observations (e.g. Güdel *et al.*, 2001; Lalitha & Schmitt, 2013; Lalitha, 2016), while flare F2 had an F/Q of ~ 34 , making it third strongest X-ray flares observed on AB Dor after the two strongest observed by BeppoSAX with F/Q ~ 100 (Maggio *et al.*, 2000). The TRS analysis shows variations in spectral parameters during the flares with peak temperatures of 43 and 92 MK with peak emission measures of 16.3 and $493 \times 10^{52} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ for flares F1 and F2, respectively. The results show that the temperature peaks at the beginning of the flare while the emission measure peaks at the peak phase, a delay seen in many solar and stellar flares (Sylwester *et al.*, 1993; van den Oord & Mewe, 1989; Stelzer *et al.*, 2002), potentially due to magnetic reconnection releasing stored magnetic energy in the corona as kinetic energy. The total X-ray energy of F1 and F2 were found to be 1.6 and $>115 \times 10^{34}$ erg indicating that these flares are very strong and are placed in the class of superflares. The global coronal abundances during flaring events have been traced and found to vary as the flare evolves, with peak abundances occurring around the peak phase of the flare. The abundances showed a 1.6 to 3.4-fold increase from their quiescent state value of $\sim 0.16 Z_{\odot}$, with the strongest flare (F2) resulting in the maximum increase. This enhancement in coronal abundance could be due to chromospheric evaporation within the flaring loop, as suggested by the increase in density within the constant volume loop during intense heating. To confirm chromospheric evaporation, the electron density of the quiescent and flaring states of AB Dor was derived using the He-like triplet from O VII emission lines. The quiescent state density was found to be 1.0 and $2.5 \times 10^{10} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ for flares F1 and F2, respectively, which is similar to or between values found in other active stars (Kuznetsov & Kolotkov, 2021; Ness *et al.*, 2002). However, during flaring states, the electron density was found to increase up to ~ 4 times the average quiescent state value, similar to previous observations of AB Dor flaring (Lalitha *et al.*, 2013). This increase in density and abundance with increasing emission measures supports chromospheric evaporation during flare rise.

Further, the semi-loop length of flares in AB Dor was derived using the hydrodynamic loop model and found to be 1.3 and $5 \times 10^{10} \text{ cm}$ for flares F1 and F2, respectively. These values are comparable to previous observations of AB Dor flares (Mason *et al.*, 2001; Güdel *et al.*, 2001; Hussain *et al.*,

2007; Lalitha *et al.*, 2013). For the Sun, typical loop lengths are around 10^9 - 10^{10} cm (Mullan, 2009). The loop heights, which are $2L/\pi$ with L being the semi-loop length, were 12-50% of AB Dor's radius, suggesting a compact corona. This was also suggested by Hussain *et al.* (2007). The total energy released by the flares was estimated to be 1.6 and $>115 \times 10^{34}$ erg, much larger than the strongest solar flares (Emslie *et al.*, 2012; Zimovets *et al.*, 2020). The total magnetic field of the loop was estimated to be 300-600 G, typical of AB Dor (Donati & Collier Cameron, 1997; Jardine *et al.*, 1999).

5 Summary and Conclusions

We have analysed the X-ray emission from the ultra-fast-rotating active star AB Dor during quiescent and flaring states. Our findings indicate the quiescent state of AB Dor comprises three temperature plasma with average temperatures, emission measures, and abundances of 0.88 keV, $6.3 \times 10^{52} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, and $0.16 Z_{\odot}$, respectively. The strongest flare F2, which occurred in 2016, was found to be the next strongest after the two strongest flares recorded from BeppoSAX observations in 1997. The peak temperature for F2 was 92 MK, and for the other flare F1, it was 43 MK. During both flares, the abundance and density increased, implying chromospheric evaporation. The loop heights of these flares did not extend beyond 50% of the star's radius, suggesting AB Dor has a compact corona.

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Data Availability

The data used in the paper is available through the XMM-Newton archive.

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